

Oxidative cyclization of phenolic Schiff bases to 2-substituted benzoxazoles promoted by tetraethylammonium superoxide under microwave irradiation

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Abstract : Rapid and efficient oxidative cyclization of phenolic Schiff bases, derived from the condensation of 2-aminophenol with aromatic aldehydes, to 2-arylbenzoxazoles is described using *in situ* generated tetraethylammonium superoxide in dry DMF, under microwave irradiation.

Keywords : Benzoxazoles, superoxide, oxidative cyclization, microwave irradiation.

Introduction

Benzoxazoles possess an array of biological properties, such as antibacterials¹, antiparasitics², fungicides³, antiinflammatories⁴, elastase inhibitors⁵, H₂-antagonists⁶, 5HT₃ receptor partial agonist⁷, anticancer activity⁸ and antituberculous activities⁹. The two most popular known strategies for synthesizing 2-substituted benzoxazoles are summarized in Scheme 1. The literature methods are based on the approaches listed 'a' and 'b'. Route 'a' involves coupling a carboxylic acid or its derivative with 2-aminophenol¹⁰. The methodology developed under strategy 'b' includes oxidative cyclization of phenolic Schiff bases, derived from the condensation of 2-aminophenol and aldehydes, using various oxidants such as PhI(OAc)₂¹¹,

Scheme 1. Retrosynthesis of 2-substituted benzoxazoles.

Mn(OAc)₃¹², thianthrene cation radical¹³, copper(I) chloride in the presence of dioxygen¹⁴, Ba(MnO₄)₂¹⁵, NiO₂¹⁶, DDQ¹⁷, Pb(OAc)₄¹⁸, Ag₂O¹⁹, active manganese dioxide²⁰, PCC supported on silica gel²¹, irradiation in the presence of NaOH with UV light²², molecular oxygen/activated carbon²³, iodine²⁴ and Cu-nanoparticles²⁵.

The use of microwave irradiation to simplify and improve classic organic reactions has become very popular technique because it often results in shorter reaction times, higher yields and cleaner reaction^{26,27}. Superoxide ion ($\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$) is a reactive species easily generated in the body which can cause serious damage to living organisms²⁸. From chemical view point, it is multipotent reagent²⁹⁻³¹ and is achieved using chemical or electrochemical method^{32,33}. Recent studies have shown that superoxide under microwave irradiation is an effective and safe reagent for conversion of aromatic amines to azo compounds³⁴ and for synthesis of organic carbamates and dithiocarbamates³⁵.

In light of the above and as a part of our ongoing research on superoxide chemistry³⁶, we report herein a rapid and efficient protocol for the synthesis of 2-arylbenzoxazoles from phenolic Schiff bases using *in situ* generated tetraethylammonium superoxide under microwave irradiation (Scheme 2).

Tetraethylammonium superoxide ($\text{Et}_4\text{N}^+\text{O}_2^-$) has been generated *in situ* by the phase transfer reaction of potassium superoxide (KO_2) and tetraethylammonium bromide ($\text{Et}_4\text{N}^+\text{Br}^-$) in dry dimethylformamide and subsequently allowed to react with a number of phenolic Schiff bases viz. 2-benzylideneaminophenol **1a**, 2-(4-methoxybenzylideneamino)-phenol **1b**, 2-(2-methoxybenzylideneamino)-phenol **1c**, 2-(2-chlorobenzylideneamino)-phenol **1d**, 2-(4-chlorobenzylideneamino)-phenol **1e**, 2-(4-tolylideneamino)-phenol **1f**, 2-(4-bromobenzylideneamino)-phenol **1g**, 2-(2-furylmethyleneamino)-phenol **1h** to bring about an oxidative cyclization to give the corresponding benzoxazoles **2a-h** in reasonably good to excellent yields, under microwave irradiation (Table 1). It is important to mention that tetraethylammonium superoxide alone in the absence of microwave was able to achieve the same transformation in considerably longer reaction time (4.5 h) with **1a**. To observe the sole role of microwave on the above reactions, some blank experiments under microwave irradiation in absence of tetraethylammonium superoxide were also carried out resulting in no net reactions. However when microwave is coupled with superoxide, the rate of reaction is dramatically enhanced, thereby highlighting the significance of microwave-superoxide combination.

The reaction was accomplished by using a 3.0 fold molar excess of KO_2 and 1.5 fold molar excess of Et_4NBr with respect to substrate **1**. Each reaction was monitored by TLC for its completion. The products were fully identified by their physical and spectral data, which are in full agreement with the values described in literature^{11,16,18,37-39}.

Experimental

Melting points were measured in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a JASCO FT/IR-5300 spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR spectra were run on a JEOL AL300 FT-NMR and the chemical shift are expressed as δ (ppm), using TMS as internal reference. Potassium superoxide and tetraethylammonium bromide were procured from E. Merck, and were used as received. Dry DMF of Aldrich, was stored over molecular sieves (4 Å) prior to use. Phenolic Schiff bases were prepared according to a literature procedure¹⁸. A Kenstar digital microwave oven at full power (800 W) was used.

General procedure for the preparation of 2a-h: A mixture of potassium superoxide (0.43 g; 0.006 mol) and tetraethylammonium bromide (0.63 g; 0.003 mol) (weighted under nitrogen atmosphere using an atmobag) in dry dimethylformamide (15 ml) was stirred for 15 min to facilitate the formation of tetraethylammonium superoxide. The phenolic Schiff base **1** (0.002 mol) was finally introduced and the contents of vessel (open) were subjected to microwave irradiation for the specified time (Table 1). The reaction-mixture was poured into a beaker containing brine solution (15 ml) and cold water (15 ml)

Table 1. Synthesis of 2-substituted benzoxazoles promoted by tetraethylammonium superoxide under microwave irradiation

Entry	R	Product	Time (MW/min)	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Lit. m.p. (°C)
1	C_6H_5	2a	3.0	87	103	102 ¹⁸
2	4- $\text{CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4$	2b	3.5	76	101	100–101 ¹⁶
3	2- $\text{CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4$	2c	4.0	72	59	59 ³⁷
4	2- ClC_6H_4	2d	3.0	82	128	128–129 ³⁸
5	4- ClC_6H_4	2e	3.0	89	148	147 ¹¹
6	4- $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	2f	3.0	85	116	115.5–116 ¹⁶
7	4- BrC_6H_4	2g	3.0	87	155–156	156–157 ³⁸
8	2-Furyl	2h	4.0	71	83	84 ³⁹

and then extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 × 20 ml). The combined organic extract was dried over Na₂SO₄ (anhyd.), filtered and evaporated to furnish a residue which was passed through silica gel column to afford the corresponding benzoxazole **2**.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the present procedure involving *in situ* generated tetraethylammonium superoxide under microwave irradiation provides a rapid and efficient method for the preparation of 2-substituted benzoxazoles from phenolic Schiff bases.

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